

University mathematics students' use of resources: Strategies, purposes, and consequences

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This contribution provides a qualitative view of mathematics students' use of resources in their first year at a German university on the basis of problem-centred interviews. Results show that students use many different material resources, such as exercises, lecture notes, books, internet, etc., as well as the help of other persons to organise their learning of mathematics. The use of the respective resources differs in various phases of the study and serves different purposes. In addition, consequences of the use of resources on exam success and the experience of success when completing exercises are examined. These results have possible implications for the conception of mathematics courses, which are discussed.

Introduction & theory

The transition from school to university, especially in mathematics, is associated with various difficulties, which are due, for example, to differences in mathematical content, or in the way mathematics is communicated, thought and taught (e.g., de Guzmán et al., 1998; Thomas & Klymchuk, 2012). These differences are also reflected in the resources that accompany mathematics learning: “teachers ‘change into’ lecturers; lessons into lectures; homework into coursework; textbooks into course materials and lecture notes; tests into examinations; and school mathematics into university mathematics” (Gueudet & Pepin, 2017, p. 469).

The term “resources” is used in many ways. Adler (2000) distinguishes human resources (e.g., other students, lecturers, their knowledge base, etc.), material resources (e.g., chalkboard, textbooks, mathematical proofs), as well as social and cultural resources (language, time, etc.). In Schoenfeld's (2011) theory of goal-oriented decision making, resources are understood as people's knowledge in the context of available materials. Together with their goals and orientations (beliefs, values, dispositions, etc.) they are expected to explain persons' actions. Accordingly, an adequate use of different resources can be regarded as an important factor for successful learning.

In quantitative studies, the use of resources is often conceptualized and operationalized within self-regulated learning theories (e.g., Panadero, 2017, for an overview) as a special class of learning strategies (e.g., Credé & Phillips, 2011). Such studies provide empirical evidence that across study programs managing one's time and study environment as well as

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using literature is positively correlated with academic performance, whereas peer learning and help-seeking are not or negatively correlated with academic performance (Boerner et al., 2005; Credé & Phillips, 2011). In mathematics courses, these correlation patterns are rather not observed, with sometimes even negative effects of the use of literature (Griese, 2017).

This paper focuses on two classes of resources: mathematics learning materials, i.e., materials such as books, lecture notes, exercises, etc., and human resources, which are understood here as other people that students can draw on for peer learning or help-seeking.

In line with Schoenfeld's (2011) theory students' goals are considered a key factor for the selection and use of the respective resources, whereby students' goals are understood as "the conscious or unconscious aims they are trying to achieve" (Schoenfeld, 2011, p. iv). The different resources of school and university entail different goals as well as different expected and actually implemented strategies of students. Rezat (2013) found that secondary school students use textbooks mainly to practice similar tasks or worked examples. At university, lecturers expect students to use lecture notes to learn and understand mathematical concepts, and as a model for certain mathematical practices, e.g., for mathematical proof construction (Gueudet & Pepin, 2018). Students use resources provided by their institution most often, but they also use many other resources (Anastasakis et al., 2017). The use of resources changes during the course of study (Stadler et al., 2013), is strongly oriented towards exam-related goals (Anastasakis et al., 2017), and depends on the institutional framework (Gueudet & Pepin, 2018; Kock & Pepin, 2018). Therefore, the structure of typical mathematics courses for first-year mathematics students at German universities will be briefly described here.

Mathematics modules of the first semesters at German universities normally consist of lectures and related exercises. The lectures introduce mathematical theory, i.e., definitions, examples, theorems and their proofs are presented. The exercises are handed out weekly and worked on by students in self-study. Students' solutions are submitted, corrected and discussed in a separate lesson. In order to pass such a module, usually a certain number of exercises (often 50% of all exercises) has to be solved correctly and a written exam has to be passed. According to the study regulations of German universities, the self-study time is about two thirds of the scheduled learning time for the respective lectures of the first academic year.

This paper examines the use of materials and learning with others by mathematics students in this institutional context. The research questions are as follows:

- RQ1 Which resources do students use when learning mathematics at university?
- RQ2 For which purposes are the respective resources used? Which goals regulate the use of resources?
- RQ3 How are the different resources used?
- RQ4 How is the use of the different resources related to the learning success of students?

Method

In order to investigate these questions, problem-centred interviews (Witzel, 2000) were conducted and analysed in two consecutive academic years with a total of 18 students (13 of whom were female) at up to four interview times in their first year of study (see Göller, 2020, for a detailed description of the study design). To recruit participants for the study, the research project was briefly presented in a mathematics lecture attended by students from various (mathematics-related) study programs. The 18 interviewees volunteered to participate in the study. Participation in the study was not compensated. Gender and age of the participants were not specified by the interviewees. The gender reported here was assigned to the interviewees by the interviewer and is intended only to provide a rough description of the sample.

Ten interviewees (9 female) were enrolled in a degree program for mathematics teachers at upper secondary level, six (3 female) in the degree program Mathematics B.Sc. and two (1 female) in the degree program Business Education. The respective interviews had a duration of about 45 minutes, were audio-recorded, completely transcribed and analysed using methods from Grounded Theory Methodology (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). The interview questions addressed key topics of self-regulated learning and Schoenfeld's theory of goal-oriented decision making, such as students' strategies, goals, beliefs, and evaluations with respect to the mathematics lectures in their first study year. The use of resources, such as mathematics learning materials and human resources, was coded as a subcategory of strategies (see Göller, 2020).

All interviewed students attended mathematics courses in the form described above in which an exam was written at the end of the semester and at least 50 % of the points of the weekly exercises had to be completed correctly during the semester in order to achieve admission to the exam.

Results

Category	Quote example
Learning with other students	
- Work on exercises	And there we always meet and try to solve the algebra exercises.
- Work on lecture contents	And then on the very last day [before the exam] we met in a group and discussed last questions.
Help-seeking	
- Other students	... sometimes I asked other students if I had not understood something.
- Lecturers	Well, sometimes we ask the lecturer herself.
- Relatives and friends	And if I get stuck, I ask my uncle.

Table 1: Categories of learning with others

All interviewees reported learning with other people. This learning with other people has different forms, which are listed in Table 1. Most of the learning with others is spent working on the exercises, with smooth transitions between working together on the exercises and seeking help from other students.

The categories of materials used by the students interviewed are listed in Table 2.

Category	Examples	Quote example
Exercises	on the attended lectures	I try to work through the exercises.
Lecture notes	of the attended lectures	Tuesday, I worked on the lecture notes.
Books	Paper books, e-books, textbooks, etc.	There are also workbooks with solutions and where you just have to look if there is something in them, some kind of trick.
Websites	Google, Wikipedia, etc.	If I didn't understand definitions or such things, I often read something on Wikipedia.
Social Networks	Facebook, WhatsApp, Phone, etc.	We have a WhatsApp group, so I photograph the exercises and put them in the group.
Videos	YouTube etc.	YouTube has also helped me a lot.
Solutions of others	Solutions of peers, worked examples, etc.	if people already worked on this [exercise] then I look at it. And then try to understand it for myself and write it down again.
Previous exams	Exams of previous years	I also worked on some old exams.

Table 2: The different materials used by the interviewees

The institutional framework of the study implies two central performance goals, which were expressed by all interviewees: Passing the exams and achieving 50 % of the points for the weekly exercises to achieve admission to the exam. Some interviewees also formulated other goals, e.g., learning goals, but overall, these two performance goals were so dominant that strategies to achieve them often superseded strategies to achieve learning goals. Moreover, these two performance goals are consecutive, in the sense that admission to the exams had to be achieved first before passing the exams was addressed. As a result, these two performance goals define two different phases in which the use of resources and associated strategies differ: During the semester students' primary goal was to find solutions for exercises in order to achieve admission to the written exams. If admission was achieved at the end of the semester, the focus shifted to the preparation for passing the exams. In the following, these two phases will be considered separately.

The use of resources during the semester

During the semester, the students' mathematical work was dominated by the exercises. All other materials were primarily used to support the work on the exercises. A follow-up of the lecture contents after the lectures beyond working on exercises was rarely reported, and in many cases explicitly denied. The most frequent strategies were working together with others on the exercises, searching for solutions or worked examples on the internet or in books, and working with solutions of others.

The use of the various resources also depends on how autonomously the interviewees were able to solve the respective exercises. Generally, the interviewees first tried to work on the exercises on their own and then, depending on their progress, drew on more and more other resources. This process is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A typical sequence of students' use of resources when working on exercises

Figure 1 describes different possible and in the interviews reported steps to generate a final solution for exercises, which can be used to illustrate the approaches of different students. For example, the following interview excerpt illustrates the steps taken by a student (S1) in the fifth week of her first semester to solve exercises:

S1: First of all, I read an exercise. At the beginning I usually think, oh my God, what is that? Then I check the lecture notes to see what we have done. Then it usually becomes a bit clearer what somebody wants from me on this exercise sheet. And then I try to write down my own thoughts about it. And if I can't get any further, I read in the book or on the internet and try to find a solution. And if I still can't get anywhere, then I put it aside and do the next one. Maybe I think about it again later. And if I still don't get ahead, then I just ask someone.

This interview excerpt shows that she first and foremost tries to solve the exercises alone, using the lecture notes (top left), then she uses other materials (middle left) and only as a last

step asks other students for help (bottom right). In the middle of the second semester, the same student reports an approach that focuses much more on working with others to solve exercises (right side):

S1: Tuesday at noon we have two and a half hours off. All from my math crew. And then we always sit together and try to solve the algebra exercises. After the two and a half hours we usually realize that we have solved maybe one and a half problems and have no idea about the rest. Since the submission deadline for the exercises is on Thursday [...], the panic breaks out at the latest on Thursday morning, when we sit together for another two and a half hours. Because still no one has a clue about two tasks. And then we talk or write to other math people, where most of them have just as little idea as we do, and then at some point we just send the solutions back and forth, copy them and hand them in.

Overall, it can be observed that collaborative working on exercises with others increases during the first study year. However, regarding Figure 1, the interviewees differ in how much time and effort they invested in the respective steps, which steps they could possibly skip, because they were able to solve the exercises on their own with the lecture notes and then only compared solutions with others,

S2: So, like I said, I'm reviewing the lecture notes first. First of all, I have to understand the exercise. I have to read it several times. And I find, especially when you look at the documents again, the lecture notes, that you always find something that you need for the exercise. [...] This is of course not the case with every problem, but that sometimes there were parts that have cross connections to the exercises, i.e., were quite similar to the exercises. I also bought literature to consult literature where it is written in more detail. And then I make my own sketches. My own approaches. Write them down. And then, as I said, we meet with the peer group and then just complement the things.

or which step they started with. For example, there are interviewees who started almost immediately to look for solutions on the internet or in books,

S3: In the beginning I really tried to solve the exercises with the lecture notes. With some exercises it still works. But in the meantime, I immediately enter keywords into Google to see if I find anything similar. Then I try to understand it. And apply it to the exercise. But it always takes too much time to first look at the lecture notes.

who almost exclusively worked on exercises with others,

S4: The main part, well, almost everything I do, I do in the group.

or even started straight away to copy solutions of others:

S5: We have a study group now, and somebody always has the solution. And most of the time I just copy them to get my admission, because there is simply no time for it.

However, the exact path of the problem-solving process always depends on the concrete exercises and in particular on how far the individual students got with which strategies. Experience of success in completing the exercises was reported especially in the context of follow-up the lecture notes.

The use of resources for exam preparation

To prepare for the exams, the same materials were used by the interviewees as for solving the exercises during the semester. However, a different focus can often be observed here: While the work with mathematical contents focused on the exercises during the semester, some interviewees (also) focused on the lecture notes during the exam preparation. In most cases, this focus on the lecture notes consisted of extracting definitions and theorems from the lecture notes and then trying to understand and remember them. The proofs of the theorems of the lecture notes were only rarely followed up by the interviewees, and by many not at all. In addition, the students prepared for the exams mainly by themselves and usually only met once with peers to discuss questions.

Table 3 shows the relationship of the interviewees' exam grades to their use of resources in the exam preparation phase.

Grade	Preparation time	Focus
12	> 2 weeks	Lecture notes, all exercises
11	3 days	Previous exams
10	> 2 weeks	Lecture notes, (procedural) exercises
9.5	3 weeks	Lecture notes, all exercises
9	> 2 weeks	Lecture notes, books
7.5	9 days	Lecture notes, all exercises
7	15 days	Lecture notes
6	2 weeks	Exercises
5.5	3 days	Lecture notes
5	2 weeks	Videos of procedures
5	1 week	Lecture notes
4	1 week	Lecture notes (selected proofs)
3	3 days	Selected (procedural) exercises

Table 4: The relationship between exam grades (15 best, 0 poorest), exam preparation time, and the focus of the use of materials during exam preparation

Interviewees who invested more time in exam preparation tended to do better in the exams. Furthermore, it can be observed that those who did better in the exams often focused on both the lecture notes and the exercises, whereas those who did poorer in the exams focused rather on specific materials. This can also often be explained by the time invested, since students usually planned to repeat both materials, starting with one of them and then often had no more time for the other.

Discussion

The results show how diverse the resources used by students are and that these resources serve different purposes in different phases of a semester. During the semester the focus is on the exercises, and all other materials as well as the support of other people are mainly used to work on them. Typically, students first try to work on the exercises on their own and then, depending on their progress, draw on more and more other resources (see Figure 1). Accordingly, the use of such additional resources can be seen as an indicator of difficulties with solving exercises autonomously, which may explain negative correlations of academic performance with literature use and peer learning (e.g., Griese, 2017).

In the exam preparation phase, several students (also) focused on the lecture notes. While cooperation with others played a major role for working on exercises during the semester, all interviewees prepared for the exams mainly on their own. The results also indicate that the follow-up of the lecture notes is the most promising way to experiences of success while completing exercises, while a longer preparation time and a repetition of both the lecture notes and the exercises is the most promising way to succeed in the exams.

The results also show a considerable impact of the institutional settings on the goals and resource use of the students, which results here in a strong focus of the students on the exercises. Gueudet & Pepin (2018) also observed a focus on exercises at a French university, while at the examined UK university the focus of the students was on the lecture notes. This focus on the exercises led in the French and the German sample examined here to the situation that several students started to look for solutions or worked examples mainly on the internet and in books. This procedure does not meet the lecturers' expectations that students use the lecture notes to learn and understand the concepts, and as a model for certain mathematical practices, e.g., for mathematical proof construction (Gueudet & Pepin, 2018).

Overall, it seems that under the pressure of constantly having to produce solutions to exercises during the semester, some students use strategies that do not necessarily seem beneficial for learning (such as copying solutions to exercises from others) and postpone strategies for achieving their learning goals and for following up lecture notes. This applies in particular to students' work with proofs: Students try to construct proofs when the exercises require them to do so, but most of the students interviewed here almost never followed up the proofs of the lectures - neither in the semester nor in the exam preparation phase.

On the other hand, the focus on the exercises provides an important institutional tool to regulate students' strategies. Accordingly, strategies and goals considered essential should be represented as explicitly as possible in the exercises. For example, special task formats can be considered which support the following up of lecture notes, in particular the reading of proofs. Particular attention must also be paid to the difficulty of the exercises in order to enable as many students as possible to work on the exercises on their own while at the same time challenge all students.

When interpreting the results, the small number of students surveyed here must be taken into account and generalizations should be treated with caution. Nevertheless, the results of this and the other studies cited here show that a detailed examination of students' use of resources can provide an important contribution to research on students' learning of mathematics and the design of mathematics courses.

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